

Virtual Reality Digital Models for Claustrophobia Treatment: Enhancing Virtual Exposure Therapy

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Abstract:

This paper describes the researchers' initial efforts to define relevant characteristics of a parameterized digital model for future use as a testing platform in virtual reality exposure therapy. Parameters in the model will register specific spatial characteristics such as wall height and horizon visibility within a given area of space. The research ultimately aims at finding a basic set of guidelines for identifying relevant thresholds of spatial and environmental constraints such as height, natural lighting, and visibility. Guidelines developed through the research could provide a framework for additional models.

Keywords:

virtual reality, psychology, spatial anxiety, exposure therapy

1. Introduction:

27.7% of the US population reported experiencing anxiety disorder symptoms in the year 2022 (CDS 2023). Anxiety disorders include agoraphobia and claustrophobia, which is the fear of enclosed, tight spaces. Over the past decade, psychologists have been using exposure therapy to treat various psychological illnesses like post-traumatic stress disorders, where gradual exposure to negative stimuli is given to patients to overcome their fears (Boeldt et al 2019; Bouchard et al 2016; de Paiva and Jedon 2019; Garcia-Palacios et al 2004; Krijn et al 2004; Pop, Matu, and Szentagotai-Tatar 2018; Powers and Emmelkamp 2008; Quesnel and Riecke 2008; Wang et al 2020; Wilson and Soranzo 2015).

In one of the most efficient treatments, psychologists use exposure therapy to help people overcome their fear of objects, activities or situations. This is done by exposing patients to the potential risks through a safe environment using pictures, videos and imagination. According to Foa and Kozak (1986)'s emotional processing theory, exposure therapy can help alter neural memory structures and replace the old anxiety-inducing ones.

Exposure therapy may assume one or more of the following therapy types:

- **In-vivo:** Patients are made to do activities where they are gradually exposed to different scenarios of trauma.
- **Imaginal:** Patients are made to vividly imagine the feared scenario.
- **Flooding:** A combination of both in-vivo and imaginal exposure therapy, but much more intensive and implemented over a longer period of time.

Although exposure therapy has been proven to be effective, only 10% - 20% of patients seek exposure therapy (Garcia-Palacios et al 2001). There is avoidance towards exposure therapy, but the introduction of virtual reality into exposure therapy has helped curb this avoidance by creating a virtual barrier between a real threat/fear and the patient, by creating a simulation of the same environment. In turn, this encourages patients to be more open to the idea of exposure therapy. Virtual reality can also help the therapist control the visuals shown to the patient, which is not the case with either imaginal or in-vivo exposure therapy. Thus, virtual reality exposure therapy (VRET) is identified as an alternative to standard in vivo exposure (Krijn et al 2004; Meyerbröker and Emmelkamp 2010). In VRET, virtual reality using real-time computer graphics, renderings, body tracking devices, visual displays and other sensory input devices may be used to immerse patients into a computer-generated virtual environment where therapeutic 'exposure' can take place.

The purpose of this study is to define relevant characteristics of a parameterized digital model for future use as a testing platform in virtual reality exposure therapy. The study aims to develop guidelines for future models that can be used by therapists and designers to do the following:

- Determine whether a person has claustrophobic tendencies.
- Develop digital models for use in exposure therapy, to help ensure slow deliberate exposure.
- Possibly in the future, help psychiatrists, psychologists and clinicians control the level of exposure, making the treatment more accessible.
- Possibly help architects make better design decisions in relation to anxiety-inducing spaces.

2. State of the Art:

3.1 Virtual reality exposure therapy vs. in-vivo exposure therapy

Stephane et al (2016) test the efficacy of treatment between virtual reality and in-vivo therapy, showing that virtual reality exposure therapy is a better alternative to in-vivo exposure therapy and has been proven to be a potential solution for treatment avoidance. Treatment avoidance is an issue where patients avoid treatment because in-person exposure is more traumatic than virtual exposure. VRET has proven to be effective in the real world and improvements were maintained after a 6-month follow up. VR technology is being used (Boeldt et al 2019) for the treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), eating disorders (ED) along with anxiety disorders. The use of virtual reality can be expected to increase in the future.

With this paper we theorize that it is important and beneficial to have quantifiable spatial characteristics. Our objective is to utilize a head-mounted display (HMD) system for tracking the head movements and visual experiences of patients. The HMD will be connected to a computer, enabling the therapist to gain real-time insight into the patient's visual perspective.

Figure 1. HMD System (Krijn et al, 2004)

This information would allow the therapist to precisely comprehend what the patient is seeing within the virtual environment. If required, the therapist can then navigate the patient through the virtual environment based on this understanding (Krijn et al 2004).

Figure 2. Virtual Reality Environment in ICube (Pop et al 2018)

Pop et al (2018) analyze how particular characteristics of space can influence the level of psychological comfort experienced by users who also experience high levels of anxiety in small and closed spaces. Their experiment studies the relationship between specific spatial characteristics like dimensions, proportions, presence or absence of furniture, and presence and absence of fenestration, according to Romanian building regulation laws. They used 3D immersive environments for the study as it provided a controlled environment. The experiment showed that the current building regulations are focused only on safety issues but not on psychological impacts.

In addition to the ability to conduct controlled experiments in a fully immersive environment, virtual reality also helps study a complex range of stimulus conditions that could not easily be controllable in the real world such as attention and functional behaviors (Boeldt et al, 2019). This helps overcome a number of limitations that come with using traditional methods like in-vivo, imaginal, and interoceptive therapy.

Our hypothesis is that we can aim to create better VR models if we understand the thresholds of spaces that can cause anxiety. This paper will aim to establish parameters for models, including specifically relevant variables. Such specificity could help create a more gradual exposure to the source of fear, which in turn could help improve the quality of treatment. We will consider how virtual reality models can be improved based on specific spatial conditions like height, light, and visibility to create opportunities for more controlled environmental analysis.

3. Methods:

3.1. First Phase:

The first phase of the study will include case study analysis of VR-based exposure therapy and studying its observations, shortcomings and potentials. This would provide us with ample information to move ahead and create diagrams and digital models.

3.2. Second Phase:

For the second phase of the study, we will use virtual reality as a tool to create scenarios that simulate progressively narrowing spaces, i. e., fear-inducing environments for claustrophobia sufferers. This phase will focus on experiments using custom virtual reality environments, interfaces, and models to provide further insight on specific spatial characteristics that might have an effect on a person's psyche, such as photometric values, different shades of color, height relativity, degree of enclosure, and visibility on patients suffering from anxiety disorders, specifically claustrophobia and agoraphobia. Our study will examine a sample of subjects suffering from diagnosed anxiety disorders, subjects with mild anxiety disorders, and subjects with no anxiety disorders. The observations will be done through foot and visual tracking from VR, followed by surveys.

3.3. Third Phase:

This stage will include data collection and experimentation. Because the project considers how virtual reality models could help treatment of patients with anxiety disorders (specifically, claustrophobia), an efficient test of its efficacy would involve the following methods:

- *Pulse oximeter.* By using a pulse oximeter, we can measure the changes in heart rate as the participant goes through the virtual reality simulation. Higher heart rate is understood as an indication of higher feelings of anxiety in the participant. We would gather substantial physiological data that in combination with survey data could support or refute this understanding. Also, collecting continuous heart rate data can allow for a more detailed analysis on specific spaces of triggers in the virtual reality model.

- *Surveys* will aid in understanding the subjective change in experiences and moods that participants might have during the virtual reality experience. By administering surveys before and after the VR experience, we can gather self-reported data on anxiety levels, mood changes, and emotional responses. Surveys provide an opportunity for participants to express their feelings, thoughts, and perceptions, which may not be fully captured by physiological measurements alone. We will attempt to correlate data from the survey responses with observational data showing increased anxiety levels reported during moments of higher heart rate.

A combination of both physiological and survey data-collection methods will be beneficial in providing a more comprehensive picture and will enable us to corroborate objective physiological responses with participants' own perceptions.

4. Results and Discussion:

4.1. Virtual Reality Model prototypes

We created four digital models with varying spatial characteristics, specifically to study the anxiety levels with respect to claustrophobia. The spatial characteristic variation is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Model Attributes Table

Model	Visibility	Height
Model 0	No Visibility	Flat Roof - Remains constant throughout model
Model 1	No Visibility	Height Gradually Increases
Model 2	Eye Level Visibility	Flat Roof - Remains constant throughout model

Model 3	Above Eye level Visibility	Height Gradually Increases
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- **Model 0:**

This model shows the most basic model created with no change in height and visibility and acts as the base model for the variations to follow.

The design of the model is based on the idea that the corridor space narrows and widens at intervals and also has turns which give opportunity for breaks and intentional movement as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 3. Plan of Model 0

Figure 4. Eye-level view of model 0

- **Model 1:**

With this model we hope to study the effects of varying wall height on levels of anxiety by addressing the relationship between the gradually increasing wall height along with movement in the model.

The ceiling height has been varied between 8ft to 20 ft. The simulation starts with the lowest height and as it moves towards the center the height is at its greatest.

Figure 5. Elevation (top) and Isometric view of Model 1

Figure 6. Eye-level view of model 1

Figure 6 shows a junction in the model where height of the model and the narrowness of the passage is visible. The aim with the scenario is to observe if increasing the height at a point of narrowness can decrease the anxiety experienced by the participant. This could also help us understand whether people experience symptoms of anxiety more with narrowness or the height of the space.

Figure 7. Grasshopper script used to make Model 1

- **Model 2:**

With this model we hope to study the effects of eye-level visibility on the anxiety experienced by the user. Visibility has been cut out by using the perpendicular of the lines of vision. The visibility openings are 2ft x 2ft and are at the height of 5.7ft.

Figure 8. Plan showing vision lines (top) and Isometric view of Model 2 with perpendicular vision lines

Figure 9. Isovist Diagrams

The isovist is a component of the space syntax toolkit, and is relevant to the present research (Benedikt 1979). Initially, the isovist can be understood in a technical sense as a graphic tool. Essentially, it serves as a diagram portraying the visible area's extent from a single point, typically depicted in plan view. Additionally, isovists can be illustrated in section (Dosen and Ostwald 2017) or volumetrically (Lonergan and Hedley 2016). Whether drawn in plan or in section, the isovist can serve as a data source in visual form. Its performance as a generator of graphic or visual data is distinct from its role in generating data as part of an isovist field (Benedikt 1979). Within the scope of the present research, there is a potential for identifying a positive correlation between (a) visual data within isovists or isovist fields and (b) physiological and/or survey data. Consequently, the isovist can act as a mechanism for detecting possible claustrophobic effects, either in plan or section. Figure 9 displays isovists produced in correspondence with unique viewpoints distributed throughout the floor plan. These distinct isovists are valuable for evaluating the overall viewshed at specific locations, but they also give rise to certain problematic issues for the research. Three such issues can be identified. Firstly, individual isovists raise the question of whether motion should be analyzed as discrete or

continuous.

Particular isovists could be selected to emphasize specific attributes of visual experience at characteristic or representative locations. Secondly, an individual isovist does not account for directionality, as it assumes a full 360-degree view. Lastly, isolated isovist diagrams fail to address the aspect of time.

Figure 10. Eye-level view of model 2

Figure 10 shows the view of the Model 3, where there are openings on the “walls” that give opportunity for visual access to the outside world. This could be a view to a forest, garden or any space that gives a visual sense of freedom.

Figure 11. Grasshopper script used to make Model 2

- **Model 3**

This model is a combination of Model 1 and Model 2, where there is a gradual increase in the ceiling height as the participant walks through the model. The ceiling height starts from a low 8ft height and ends with a height of 12ft as the participant moves towards the center of the model.

In this model, openings have been strategically placed at a 10° angle from the line of sight, offering an elevated view beyond the eye level.

Figure 12. Perspective view of Model 3 (top) and Vision lines of Model 3

Figure 13. Eye-level view of model 3

The intention behind the design choice to place windows above eye level is to investigate the impact of having visibility above eye level. By exploring the effects of this architectural feature, we aim to gain insights into its potential influence on spatial experiences and perception.

Figure 14. Grasshopper script used to make Model 3

5. Conclusion:

Using our observations from this study, we further intend to create a technological upgradation for the use of (VRET) virtual reality based exposure therapy. In this process we wish to record the effects of different scenarios on users with no prior claustrophobic experience.

This research hopes to create possibilities for further investigation on how identifying certain architectural spatial characteristics can be used to create more personalized models for the purpose of virtual reality exposure therapy.

By identifying the thresholds of spatial characteristics that may trigger feelings of anxiety, we can incorporate these findings into architectural design to create more comfortable and accommodating spaces. This research holds potential for enhancing our understanding of how architectural elements can be used to improve spatial experience.

Looking ahead, these improved models have the potential to revolutionize the usability of virtual reality by involving therapists more actively in the design process and granting them greater control over the models. This increased involvement allows for personalized customization based on the specific needs and preferences of each patient. By bridging the gap between architectural design and therapy, we aim to create a future where virtual reality becomes a more impactful tool for personalized treatment and patient well-being.

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